

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B030
Date: 17 Jul 2004
Take Off: 15:00:47
Landing: 20:19:18
Flight Time: 5h18m31

Trials Instructions: ITOP - Interception and characterisation of N American pollution from a range of sources

Operating Area: SW of the Azores

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Allan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Allan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Paul Monks	Leicester University
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	James Lee	York University
7	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
8	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
9	Observer	Debbie Wylding	UEA
10	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
11	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
12	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
13	TDL	Will Flynn	Cambridge University
14	Mission Scientist 2	Claire Reeves	UEA
15	WAS/PAN	Ruth Purvis	York University
16	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
17			
18			

Track Plot:

B030 Track 1 / -JUL-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B030
 Date: 17 July 2004
 Project: ITOP
 Location: Horta, Azores

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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150047		T/O	-.03 kft	089	
150823	150953	Run 1	10.0 - 10.3 kft	217	
151645	152649	Run 2	14.0 kft	219	
151930					end JW cal
152710					PSAP flow off
152745					PSAP flow on
152825	153926	Profile 1.1	14.0 - 5.0 kft	122	1000ft/min
153710					PSAP flow off
153941	154718	Profile 1.2	4.9 - 0.83 kft	114	
155016	160015	Profile 2	0.83 - 9.0 kft	257	
155904		EVM	8.1 kft	257	Claire 1
160036	165550	Run 3	9.0 kft	253	
160115					PSAP flow on
160145					PSAP flow off
161350					PSAP flow on
161846		EVM	9.0 kft	276	Claire 2
162100					PSAP flow off
162550					PSAP flow on
162912					PSAP flow off
163030					PSAP flow on
164000					SATCOM call, CCM to DFL
165625	170856	Profile 3	9.0 - 3.0 kft	272	
170006		EVM	7.4 kft	270	Paul 1
170906	172733	Run 4	3.0 kft	267	
172210		EVM	3.0 kft	287	Paul 2
173335	175802	Run 5	3.0 kft	086	
174800					TWC reset
175830	180257	Profile 4	3.0 - 5.0 kft	086	
180444	181801	Run 6	5.0 kft	340	
181814	182158	Profile 5	5.0 - 3.0 kft	342	
182206	182858	Run 7	3.0 kft	345	
182530					PSAP flow off
182912	183255	Profile 6	3.0 - 5.0 kft	346	
183135					PSAP flow on
183436	184519	Run 8	5.0 - 4.9 kft	094	
184535	185418	Profile 7	4.9 - 0.01 kft	090	500ft/min
184916					PSAP flow off
185425	190420	Run 9	0.1 kft	087	
190052					Heimann cal 12
190110					PSAP flow on
190514	191307	Profile 8	0.02 - 3.4 kft	087	
190645					PSAP flow off
192100					PSAP flow on
192418	192820	Run 10	4.9 kft	089	
194556	194906	Run 11.1	6.9 kft	300	
195955	200209	Run 11.2	6.9 kft	293	
200436	200641	Run 12.1	5.9 kft	107	
200850	201125	Run 12.2	4.9 kft	290	
201220					PSAP flow off
201321					PSAP flow on
201918		Land	-.06 kft	086	
202255	final	GPS posn:	38 31.26N 28 43.00W		
202330	final	INU posn:	38 30.93N 28 42.56W		

B030 Track 17-JUL-04

36°W 35°W 34°W 33°W 32°W 31°W 30°W 29°W 28°W

38°N

38°N

37°N

37°N

36°N

36°N

36°W 35°W 34°W 33°W 32°W 31°W 30°W 29°W 28°W

ITOP – Interception and characterisation of N.American pollution from a range of sources

Mission Scientists: Paul Monks and Claire Reeves

Date: 17/7/04

Outline schedule:

09:00 - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

13:00 - Air Crew Briefing

14:15 – Clear aircraft

14:30 – Boarding deadline

15.00 - Take-off

Location: S.W. of the Azores

Aim: To intercept air sampled by the P3 on 15/07/04 at around 40N, 60W with 120-150 ppb of CO. This air was forecast to have picked up both anthropogenic and natural emissions from S.E US. Also to survey above and below this air mass where we expect to sample air of contrasting origins (including sub-tropical marine air). Wish to stay in clear air. Cloud is expected to the east of the feature.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take off. Climb to FL150 at 1000ft/min, interrupting for a run of 5-10 minutes at 5000ft for wet chemistry check (30).
2. T+30 Transit to 35N, 29W staying clear of cloud (expected to the east) (70).
3. T+100 Profile descent on a heading of around 260 degrees (into wind). Descent rate of 1000ft/min to 5000ft and 500ft/min to 100ft (25).
4. T+125 Profile ascent to 500ft at 500ft/min and perform a 10 minute straight and level run (10).
5. T+135 Profile ascent to FL180 at 1000ft/min (20).
6. T+155 Profile descent on reciprocal at 500ft/min, interrupting at 2 to 3 levels (1 at about 6-7000ft) to perform straight and level runs of 15 mins (75)
7. T+230 Ascend at 1000ft/min and transit to Horta at FL 170 (100)
8. T+330 Search pattern over NNE of Pico as available
9. T+340 Land at Horta.

Ground power is required at Horta for one and half hours following flight.

Flight B030 17th July 2004 Report

The aim of the flight was to sample N. American pollution sampled by the P3 on 15/07/04 at around 40N, 60W with 120-150 ppb of CO. This was forecast to the SW of the Azores in a filament orientated WSW to ENE and sloping upwards to the south. This feature was also forecast to be moving eastwards at a rate of about 2 degrees per 6 hours. Ahead and to the south of this feature substantial cloud was forecast. At low altitudes also to the east air on route for Haute Provence was forecast.

Unfortunately due to bad weather forecast at Horta for our landing, the sortie brief was altered to reduce the length of the flight to allow us to return to Horta with 1 hour full reserve. This meant that we chose not go so far south and therefore we are unlikely to have intersected the air forecast to go to Haute Provence. We worked mostly along the latitude line of 36°40'N.

On Run 3 between 36.4N, 29.3W and 36.6N, 33.3W at 9000ft we intersected the pollution filament with CO concentrations of just over 80 ppb (compared to 75 ppb at this level and 65 ppb at 1000 ft) and O3 concentrations of 60 ppb (compared to 20 ppb both at this level and 1000 ft). There were good CO and O3 positive correlations in this run. CO2 concentrations were also elevated.

In Profile 3 from 9000 ft to 3000 ft (36.7N, 33.4W to 36.6N, 34.3W) we then descended down through the filament again with CO concentrations above 90 ppb and O3 of around 55 ppb at around 7000 ft.

In Run 4 at 3000 ft we again passed through the feature. CO increased to about 85 ppb compared to below 70 ppb to the west. O3 increased only slightly from about 25 ppb either side of the feature to 30 ppb. Run 5 was a reciprocal of Run 4 so we cur back through the feature again. These runs were from 36.6N, 34.3W to 36.9N, 35.4W and back to 36.6N, 33.2W.

We then profiled up to 5000 ft (P4) and turned on a 340° heading (R6) and cut straight through the feature again, this time reaching CO and O3 concentrations of 95 ppb and 50 ppb respectively. There were more filaments to this feature with a second pollution feature of sandwiched between air with marine boundary layer characteristics.

On the return we did a 10 minute run at 100ft to look from aerosol.

When we returned to Horta the weather had improved so we were able to do 3 race track patterns at 7000, 6000 and 5000 ft to the NE of Pico.

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...030...

Date17/07/2004...

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Video Tapes	GPS	INU	DRS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
V8	Lat 38 31.26	38 31.26	HORACE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
No.	Long 28 42.98	28 43.00	SATCOM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ends	Time 14 38 10	14 39 45	
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC	Status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
14 38 53		INU → NAV						
		Reboot HORACE - not recording to optical disc						
15 00 47		TAKE OFF						
15 09 30		END J-W CAL						
15 27 10		PSAP Flow interrupt, in cloud						
15 27 45		PSAP Flow on						
15 28 25		START PROFILE 1.1			1000 ft/min			descent rate
15 37 10		PSAP flow interrupt, in cloud						
15 50 16		START PROFILE 2			1000 ft/min			ascent
16 00 15		end profile 2						
16 01 15		PSAP flow on						
16 01 45		PSAP flow off						
16 08 00		HORACE hdg 262°, Flight deck 273°						
16 13 50		PSAP flow on						
16 21 00		PSAP flow off						
16 25 50		PSAP flow on						
16 29 12		PSAP flow off						
16 30 30		PSAP flow on						
16 40 00		SATCOM, CCM → Peter Chappell						
17 27 33		end of run 4, then gap to start run 5 but run 5 could be extended to end of run 4						
17 48 00		noticed TWC not producing data. Turned off/on and started working ok.						

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B030 17/7/04

Instruments

TWC failed to record for first half of flight. Switched off/on - data then ^{produced} ~~displayed~~ ok.

RADALT no signal

HORACE plots - data can lag behind realtime by several minutes.

HORACE not recording to optical disc at pre-flight time. HORACE re-booted and all ok.

Aircraft